

GENERAL LECTURE 5

Adhesive Bonding and Composites

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ABSTRACT

Structural adhesive bonding plays an important double rôle in relation to advanced fibre composite structures. The first, probably most significant, rôle of adhesive bonding is that of an example for the composite technology. The second, more direct, rôle of bonding is its application as one of the important means for joining composite structural elements among themselves as well as with non-composite structural materials.

INTRODUCTION

When Dr. Norman A. De Bruyne at Duxford, U.K. on December 4, 1941, made the first adhesive bonded metal joint with structural strength properties,

FIG. 1 Dr. N.A. De Bruyne, the father of structural adhesive bonding and composite structures.

he could not foresee what a tremendous development his invention would see in and outside the world of aeronautical engineering (1). Neither could he foresee that another brainchild of his, the high-strength fibre reinforced plastic material (January 12, 1937) would become the forerunner of a material that nowadays is seen as one of the most promising structural materials for the turn of the centuries. (2)

Having had the privilege to be rather well acquainted with the ingenious De Bruyne and the story of his inventions it was obvious to this author that the subject of "bonded joints in composite structures" could not be dealt with, without discussing "adhesive bonding and advanced composites". That was not only for reason of the fact that both inventions historically were so closely related, they are technologically seen closely related as well.

Fig. 2 Experimental Spitfire fighter aircraft fuselage developed by Dr. N.A. de Bruyne and his team of Aero Research Ltd. in 1940. Apart from the main spar members and certain pick-up fittings the structure was laminated entirely out of "Gordon Aerolite", a unidirectional flax reinforced phenolic prepreg material. The weight matched that of the earlier metal version. (Photo courtesy CIBA-GEIGY Plastics Division).

As structural adhesive bonding has seen a much earlier development into operational aircraft structures and on a much wider scale than fibre reinforced plastic materials, the lessons learned with the former method may be important study material for those who struggle towards successful applications of advanced fibre reinforced structural materials.

Both technologies brought about not only new principles of manufacture of aircraft structures, but also demanded a completely new design approach as well. Conventional metal structures were manufactured by machining, cutting, drilling and forming of semi-manufactured materials, that subsequently were assembled by readily available means of fastening, screws, bolts, pins or rivets. The compositions and the mechanical properties of those materials used, had to meet exactly specified values. Verification took place by means of statistically justified sampling and testing of representative specimens. An effective stress- and stiffness analysis in combination with good workmanship would guarantee that a satisfactory operational result would be reached.

For the realization of both adhesive bonded as well as composite structures semi-manufactured chemical products have to be processed by the manufacturer of the structure in combination with conventional materials and components. The end-results depend strongly upon:

- the properties of the chemical components,
- the correctness of the applied processes,
- the accuracy of the processing during manufacturing.

The control of the quality cannot be done by mere inspection of the end-product, it must be based on an effective system of inspections, tests and measurements before, during and at the end of the manufacturing sequence in order to guarantee that the structure will fulfil the expectations of the designers. In both cases these complications were accepted as a consequence of the strong

desire to create structurally more efficient constructions, initially for aerospace applications; somewhat later also serving more general, but important, engineering purposes.

STRUCTURAL ADHESIVE BONDING

A structural bonded joint has a number of typical characteristics. The fastening element, the adhesive resin, is a thin, non-metallic, layer that replaces the traditional metal mechanical components. That fastener is of an organic polymeric plastic nature, that is formed out of monomeric components during a well defined chemical curing reaction process.

Another, but completely different, aspect of adhesive bonding is the adhesion of the fastening element, the adhesive resin layer, to the adherend metallic substrate. At that interface, resin/metal, complex phenomena of physical and chemical nature must result in an intimate contact between these different materials in order to guarantee an efficient and durable means of load transfer.

It must be regarded as remarkable that De Bruyne, the typical scientist, attacked both aspects from the more fundamental side. At a very early date he not only developed theories about the adhesion and other interface phenomena, (3) as well as the stress distribution in adhesive bonded joints, but also he devoted his time to develop durable resin systems and materials, such as honeycomb core for sandwich structures, that he considered as one of the means for achieving weight optimized structures. (4) Finally he was very close to the realisation of his ideas in the actual manufacturing stage as well.

Let us look back now and see what has happened with adhesive bonding and its applications in aircraft structures during these forty years. In England the De Havilland and a few other companies worked from the earliest moment with De Bruyne during the war years. My Company, Fokker, in the Netherlands came some years later, but we were also taught the original faith from the "master" himself. Not only did we learn the available know-how, but moreover the deep conviction of the necessity to thrive for understanding the fundamentals of all aspects of the complex bonded joints. e.g. the materials, processing, quality control as well as design. Gradually, the idea of adhesive bonding spread over the aeronautical world. The wish to profit from the promised advantages of adhesive bonded structures won over the still existing reluctance to adopt such an exotic manufacturing process. It is with some regret that it must be stated that in spite of the enormous potential of adhesive bonding, industrywide seen, the application cannot be considered as all-out successful. A number of reasons can be mentioned as grounds for this rather disappointing result. A situation that has even developed that far, that this author recently had to "sell" adhesive bonded structures to customers of his company against competition that defined it as an asset of their product that it contained only a limited amount of adhesive bonding and thus guaranteeing a high durability.

Most of the early designers of bonded structures had a traditional engineering background, they were well versed in the design of mechanically fastened joints. They had only a vague knowledge about the nature of these new materials, that replaced the traditional fasteners. In the back of their minds they hoped that their available knowledge and experience about metals, still would be applicable. The complex elasto/plastic stress/strain behaviour of these resinous materials, however, fooled many a designer or manufacturing engineering during the many years since the invention of Norman De Bruyne. They had insufficient knowledge how the properties of these materials were influenced by such parameters as: chemical composition of the components, operating temperature, humidity and rate of stressing, exposure to solvents (p.e. phosphate ester oils, fuels), curing-time/-temperature history and -pressure. The stress-men had a difficult time as well. De Bruyne, already, reported how the old theory of Volkersen (5) happened to give him the idea to develop a method for calculation of the stress distribution in bonded overlap joints. (6) His calculation method since then was refined by many stress analysts and to-day a multitude of

advanced computer-based methods are available. (7)

In order to achieve a strength calculation of a bonded structure to a level of reliability as achieved with the traditional mechanically joined structure, it was mandatory that realistic and accurate mechanical properties of the cured adhesive material were introduced into such calculations. Is it not an unfortunate situation that today after forty years of structural bonding, the suppliers of these primary adhesive materials still cannot provide the complete data that the designers need to do their work satisfactorily? Only in recent years the adhesive manufacturers carry out qualification and certification programs that show the influences of the environmental conditions on standardized specimens. However, it is a pity that the results of that work are not straight-away usable as a design base for the stress-men. The testresults from the standardized specimens show trends of the environmental stability of the materials, but the data cannot be used in the stress calculations. Therefore, actual material properties must be introduced. This leads to a situation that in addition to the data provided by the adhesive manufacturers the users still have to undertake many tests in order to generate the necessary design data. Fig. 3. Moreover, the nature of these "structural materials" and their components is in general kept a company secret by the manufacturers of such chemical products. While the constituents and the property variations of structural metal alloys have been early subject of international standardization and the metallurgical industry is supplying detailed literature about all design and manufacturing aspects of their products, fig. 4, the manufacturers of structural adhesives do not supply this indispensable information to the users. They have continued to leave their customers with riddles to solve. When an adhesive salesman goes around the world with a new attractive looking product, that might solve important current problems for his customers, he will easily create upto \$ 100.000,- or more laboratory work per customers' address due to the fact that the designers need different information and more than the material manufacturer can supply. The laboratories of the adhesive users have to invest much money in sophisticated analysis and testequipment and have to employ highly qualified laboratory personnel in order to find out what the nature of these structural materials might well be. Fig. 5. The described situation has certainly been one of the elements that has prevented to build up full confidence in these structural organic materials.

As mentioned earlier, De Bruyne made an effort to understand a.o. the nature of the interface phenomena. His work was continued by a few of the early adhesive bonding using industries. (8) Others, however, overlooked the complexity and fundamental nature of this particular aspect, a result of that was that unfortunately on a large scale adhesive bonded structures have been produced and installed in aircraft, that would later in operation show an insufficient interface stability, causing many operational problems. Fig. 6. A worldwide investigation into the durability of adhesive bonded aircraft structures showed a.o. that the amount of repair- and rebuilding effort required on adhesive bonded honeycomb sandwich structures contributed to excessive maintenance costs with both commercial and military aircraft operators. Detailed investigation showed that the sources of these troubles were obvious to insiders and could have been prevented by appropriate material choice, detail design as well as process control, (9). Also the indispension by complicated and also expensive time-consuming nondestructive testing methods, that some companies thought to be absolutely indispensable for a good success, were neglected by others. Fig. 7. Also in this way they contributed to the controversial position of adhesive bonding. In this respect, it must be acknowledged, that after a considerable number of such operational durability problems had troubled the products of some of those aircraft bonding companies, the latter became also aware of the necessity to dig much deeper and build up a more fundamental knowledge about various aspects of bonding leading to considerable improvements and full benefit of bonded structures, also for their products. However, too many disappointed others quit bonding and bonded structures application without further concentrated efforts towards improvement.

ADVANCED COMPOSITES

As mentioned earlier, the introduction of advanced fibre composites has considerable similarity with that of structural adhesive bonding due to the nature of the materials and the processes that are used in order to manufacture the ready product. Unfortunately, the problem is, no doubt, even more complex. The greater number of different constituents causes the number of parameters that can influence the final result to be larger. The designer in cooperation with the stress engineer "designs" in this case the material to fit the local structural conditions. The fact that the material can be "composed" to fit these requirements is the basic attraction of composite materials. All what is done is to imitate as closely as possible the beautiful examples that the structures of nature show us everyday. (10) Fig. 8. Not only the properties of the cured matrix resins and of the used fibres play an important role, but also the strength of the interfaces resin/fibre surface; local fibre-orientation as well as volume fraction are of crucial importance for the satisfactory properties of the final endproduct.

The scopes of this and many earlier conferences on advanced fibre composite material structures are by themselves strong indications of the fact how thoroughly many aspects of these "materials for the future" are studied during numerous theoretical and experimental study-, research- and development programs. An effort that, in comparison with the early bonding period, certainly is much larger. The important question remains whether at the crucial moment of larger scale introduction into p.e. primary airliner components all such aspects can and will be taken into account by all those involved in: material selection, design, stress analysis, production planning, quality control and last but not least the manufacturing personnel and their responsible managers.

The described situation, that refined stress analysis methods have been developed for adhesive bonded structures requiring an adequate input regarding the adhesive material properties in order to lead to reliable results, is repeated in this case. All manufacturers of matrix resins and prepregs advertise the attractive features of their latest products. But how many of these manufacturers of "primary" aerospace structural materials indicate into detail the critical concentrations or tolerances of the main matrix constituents and the sensitivity of the mechanical properties (stress/strain relation) for such parameters as: uncured storage ageing conditions, curing-time/-temperature history, exposure to operational environmental conditions, etc.? The amount of testing work that has to be done by the responsible composite user companies in order to provide adequately significant data to their design and quality control departments is even more than ever was required for bonding. Fig. 9.

To-date there is an overwhelming number of indications that advanced composites really will be materials for the future, a future that does not need to be so far away. In order that such a future will be a bright one, it is mandatory that the mistakes and mishaps of adhesive bonding shall not be repeated. All-out composite introduction must be based on full information about the materials and processes used and a closed system of quality control measures. That is the only way to prevent superfluous safety margins in design, that will make composite structures less efficient and therefore less attractive for the user. Moreover, it will prevent operational troubles that will cause anti-propaganda and reluctance in the adoption in future structures. A plea is made to all those concerned with composites to avoid the duplication of the adhesive bonding story as described.

ADHESIVE BONDING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

In spite of the fact that the structurally ideal composite structure should be made as one integral component for full structural efficiency, limitations of different nature (production technology; efficiency; quality control; operational inspection) are reason for use of joints between structures out of composites among themselves as well with those out of other materials.

In addition to these reasons on which adhesive metal bonding was based, bonding offers for composites some special attractions. Mechanical, bolted and riveted, joints rely upon an adequate bearing- and load transfer capacity of the holes. That requirement can not always be met easily with holes in advanced fibre composite laminates that cut through load carrying fibres at various angles and at various depths in the material. An alternative in the form of bonding therefore is very wellcome in this particular field. Similar as is the case with metal bonding, bonding composite recognizes the following main problems areas:

- interface strength and stability
- cohesive properties of the cured adhesive resin layer

In addition to those, there is the problem of the general compatability of the adhesive and composite resin systems.

The Interface

The minimum prerequisite for a good bond is ability of the adhesive molecules to come within the range of active molecules of the adherend surface. They must "wet" the surface. Therefore it is necessary that the surface tension of the liquid adhesive is lower than the critical surface tension of the adherend. Surface contamination by materials with a low critical surface tension like PVC; PVF; PTFE can be cause for insufficient wetting by the adhesive in the liquid state. On the otherhand the morphology of the surface must be optimum for effective load transfer. This means that the effective surface area onto which adhesion can take place must be as large as possible and moreover allows as much as possible penetration of the mobile liquid adhesive. Thus, creating a mechanical anchoring of the cured molecules in the crevices of the adherend surface. This, however, without weakening the adherend surface itself. There are two other important requirements that the adhesive/adherend interface must fulfil. The interface must be "well defined" and it must be stable. The last-mentioned condition can be met better than the former in the case of CFRP composite bonding. With "well defined" is meant, that the surface, to be bonded, that is known as yielding optimum interface characteristics is clearly recognizable. Furthermore, that the processes required for creating such a surface are both reproducible and controllable. In that respect a parallel to surface treatment aluminium alloy substrates can be drawn.

An aluminium adherend surface for optimum adhesion can be created by etching in chromic-/sulphuric acid and followed by chromic acid anodizing along well specified concentrations, temperature, time, etc., etc. (8). Extensive studies have shown that the process concerned, when kept under careful surveillance will yield a typical oxyde-configuration of a well defined morphology and wettability. It can be guaranteed that with the necessary operational precautions the specified process will yield the required adherend surface configuration. Fortunately the optimum oxyde configuration is readily recognizable with the help of a suitable electron microscope as well as special equipment (Fig. 10) as the Fokker Contamination Tester, based upon electron emission energy measurement principles. Fig. 11. The virtue of the aluminium surface treatment is the fact that it is a process, that removes the ill-defined original oxyde skin and replaces it by a new, well defined, one. In the case of a cured composite surface, it is also ill-defined. It carries the history of the curing process. In the case it was cured in direct contact with a mould, almost certainly the surface is contaminated by release agents from the mould surface. If a "peelply" has been used on the composite, the peeled surface after removal of the peelply can be contaminated by residues of low critical surface tension material constituting the peelply fibres. In addition, after removal of the peelply the peeled surface may show pulled out resin areas, providing sources for inclusions and porosity in the bondline.

Various reports indicate, that the most reliable method is abrasion of the CFRP composite surface by means of sanding or blasting. (11) That process, anyway, is able to create a "new", virgin, surface, free from all sorts of undefined contaminations and adsorbed materials.

Regarding the discussion about the degree of abrasion that is required for optimum wetting, the comment can be given that the critical surface tension of cured epoxy resin is practically equal to that of carbon fibre. (12) So, from a wetting point of view, there is no real preference for entire removal of the toplayer onto the first fibre layer. An absolute complete coverage of the entire adherend surface by abrasion is however required. Whether the abrasion onto the first fibre layer would be preferable from the point of view of morphology, allowing penetration of liquid adhesive and subsequent anchoring in the surface, cannot be answered to-date yet. The risk of damage to the outer fibre layer should not be underrated.

Abrasion by sanding or fine gritblasting seeming to be the preferred surface treatment, one will readily appreciate that the condition "well defined" can only be satisfied when a highly mechanized and well controlled abrasion process is applied. The second condition to be fulfilled is the requirement for stability of the interface under various environmental influences. That condition can be satisfied much easier in the case of advanced composite than with metal-bonding.

It is an accepted fact that the adhesive energy (work of adhesion) on an epoxy resin/aluminium oxide interface is rather positive in an inert medium (+232 mJ/m²) but negative in water (-137 mJ/m²) (13); with an epoxy/carbon₂ epoxy interface this is positive in both conditions, e.g. 88-99 resp. 22-44 mJ/m². This indicates that the environmental stability of the composite/adhesive interface is high even under extreme humidity conditions, where the aluminium oxide/epoxy interface is clearly unstable.

The adhesive for composite bonding

In addition to meeting the requirements coming forth from the interface, the adhesive selection for composite bonding must be based on a few other aspects as well. Typical for the design of a bonded joint is the attention to be spent for avoidance of tensile (peel-) stresses in the adhesive layer. Adhesives with a high plastic elongation at failure are preferred due to their low sensitivity for stress concentrations at the bonded joint edges. Such stress concentrations result both from the differential deformation of the adherends as well as eccentricities in the loading of the joints. Thin, so-called "pinched-off", glue-layers are also sources of stress concentrations in bonded joints. Control of bondline thicknesses at edges as well as tapering of adherends are beneficial. These requirements are valid for bonded joints in composites as well as metals.

In the metal situation, however, there fails the typical anisotrope configuration of the composite adherends. Could in the metal situation a high plastic strain in the adhesive be sufficient, in the composite adherend a high plastic strain at failure becomes also a requirement for the matrix resins in the composite. If not, the stress concentrations caused by the bonded joint may lead to interlaminar cracking of the matrix resins.

In the case of an attempt to cocure an entire composite structure, the matrix resins act also as adhesive. As in particular the matrix resins that cure at higher temperatures (150°C and higher) have rather low plastic strain at failure, this phenomenon should not be overlooked in these "hidden" bonded joints. The decision to cocure with or without an additional bondfilm with high plastic strain at failure, should be taken only after verification in realistic testing has shown that the loading condition and the stress-strain behaviour of the resins are suitable for the particular conditions. In cases of doubt addition of extra plasticity is always advisable.

CONCLUSION

The experience with structural adhesive bonding of metals offers important lessons for the introduction of composite primary structures. For successful adhesive bonding of composites, it is important to achieve well defined adherend surfaces. In order to prevent problems with stress concentrations at the edges of

bonded joints, it is advised to look into the stress/strain characteristics of both the adhesive and the composite matrix resins.

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ADHESIVE MATERIAL PROPERTIES

STRESS/STRAIN DATA

TENSION, COMPRESSION, SHEAR

IN RELATION TO:

- STRAIN RATE
- CURING CONDITIONS
 - + HEAT-UP RATE
 - + TEMPERATURE
 - + TIME
- ENVIRONMENT
 - + TEMPERATURE
 - + HUMIDITY
 - + FLUIDS (FUEL, OILS)

FAILURE CHARACTERISTICS

- STRESS INTERACTION
- FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

FIG. 3 REQUIRED DESIGN INFORMATION FOR STRUCTURAL ADHESIVES (14)

FIG. 4 Typical information document giving engineering data for designers of metal aircraft structures. (Courtesy: ALCOA).

FIG. 5 Users of structural materials have to invest heavily in expensive laboratory equipment in order to understand these materials sufficiently. (photograph: Fokker).

Fig. 6 a, b.
Two typical examples of unnecessary low durability of adhesive bonded structures that descredited adhesive bonding seriously.

Fig. 6 c. Low interface stability was cause for many delaminations in adhesive bonded joints.

FIG. 7 a Early prototype of Fokker Bondtester (1952), instrument for nondestructive quality control of bonded joints.

FIG. 7 b Current model Fokker Bondtester (1970).

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIG. 8 Nature shows us every day beautiful examples of efficient composite structures in the form of human skeleton components (a) in which the fibres are orientated in optimum direction (b) and wood (c).

COMPOSITE MATERIAL EVALUATION

. MATRIX RESIN IDENTIFICATION

- + INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (IR)
- + HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY (HPLC)
- + GEL PERMEATION CHROMATOGRAPHY (GPC)
- + DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY, EXOTHERM, T_g (DSC)
- + GEL TIME DETERMINATION

. FIBRE IDENTIFICATION AND BUNDLE STRENGTH

. PREPREG EVALUATION UNCURED

- + WEIGHT PER AREA
- + TACKINESS
- + RESIN CONTENT
- + FIBRE CONTENT
- + VOLATILE CONTENT
- + RESIN FLOW

. PREPREG EVALUATION CURED

- STRESS/STRAIN DATA
 - + INTERLAMINAR SHEAR
 - + TENSILE, COMPRESSION
 - + FLATWISE TENSILE

IN RELATION TO:

- + STRAIN RATE
- + CURING CONDITIONS
 - , HEAT-UP RATE
 - , TEMPERATURE
 - , TIME
- + ENVIRONMENT
 - , TEMPERATURE
 - , HUMIDITY
 - , FLUIDS (FUEL, OILS)

- FAILURE CHARACTERISTICS

- + STRESS INTERACTION
- + DAMAGE TOLERANCE

FIG. 9 Data required in order to ensure material introduction with a minimum of risk.

FIG. 10 a Relation between aluminium oxide morphology after various etching qualities and fitness for bonding. The micro-etchpit configuration is optimum. (Fokker).

FIG. 10 b Optimum surface morphology of aluminium after etching and anodizing. (Fokker).

FIG. 11 Fokker Contamination Tester instrument for quality control of bond-surfaces, based on surface potential difference.